

Investigation on the Reaction of *m*-Xylohydroquinone with D-Galactose and D-Glucosamine: Spectrophotometric Studies

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The reaction of *m*-xylohydroquinone with D-galactose and D-glucosamine, the known constituents of chorionic gonadotropin, has been studied spectrophotometrically in the U.V. region. D-Galactose appears to react directly and quickly, whereas D-glucosamine exhibits a delayed reaction.

The compound, *m*-xylohydroquinone, the synthetic active principle of the oil of *Pisum sativum* (Linn.) and useful as an oral contraceptive, has been shown to possess anti-gonadotropic activity¹. This was attributed to the interaction of this compound and chorionic gonadotropin, as studied *in vitro* by spectrophotometric investigations². Pure *m*-xylohydroquinone shows an absorption maximum at 290 $m\mu$ (Fig. 1) and chorionic gonadotropin shows no proper absorption maximum, whereas the mixture, kept for some time, shows an absorption maximum at 260 $m\mu$ ² (more accurately 262 $m\mu$). The chorionic gonadotropin^{3,4} is known to be a complex protein, containing D-galactose and D-glucosamine. Therefore, the interactions of these two monosaccharides and *m*-xylohydroquinone have been studied and the results are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dilute aqueous solutions were prepared with *m*-xylohydroquinone, D-galactose, and D-glucosamine. Their absorption curves were studied individually in a Beckman spectrophotometer at intervals of 1 $m\mu$ near the region of maximum absorption and 5 $m\mu$ at other regions of U.V. range against water as solvent blank. A solution of *m*-xylohydroquinone is liable to easy oxidation in presence of air and light. Every solution was therefore charged with nitrogen gas and was kept away from light. Subsequently mixtures of *m*-xylohydroquinone (5.4×10^{-3} %) and D-galactose (4.8×10^{-2} %) as well of *m*-xylohydroquinone (5.1×10^{-3} %) and D-glucosamine (2.53×10^{-1} %) were prepared and their absorption curves were determined as before at different intervals of time.

The concentrations refer to the final concentrations in the mixture. The reference solutions of pure substances also had the same final concentrations.

Reagents were all of pure quality and deoxygenated water was used in preparing the solutions. Results have been shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

1. Sanyal, *Cal. Med. J.*, 1952, 49, 354.

2. Sanyal and Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 19, 356.

3. Fieser and Fieser, "Natural Products related to Phenanthrene", A.C.S. Monograph series, 1949.

4. Burrows, "Biological Action of Sex Hormones", Cambridge University Press, 1949.

DISCUSSION

From the curves it could be observed that *m*-xylohydroquinone starts reaction with D-galactose rather early. A study of the absorption curve within 15 minutes of mixing the two compounds shows the changes (not shown in Fig. 1) which, although slight, are definitely indicative of the beginning of a chemical reaction. Formation of a complex between the two can be assumed by the appearance of a sharp and new absorption maximum at 262 μ (Fig. 1) which is not present in the spectra of the individual compounds, viz., *m*-xylohydroquinone and D-galactose (at the same concentration as in the mixture). The nature of the curve, observed in the present case, is almost similar to that previously observed with the mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone and chorionic gonadotropin, where the formation

FIG. 1. *m*-Xylohydroquinone (0.0054%) + D-galactose (0.484%).

GLUCOSAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE (0.252%)
+
m-XYLOHYDROQUINONE (0.0055%)
▲ OBSERVED INTERACTION DELAYED (AFTER
24 HOURS)
■ OBSERVED INTERACTION IMMEDIATE (5 MIN)
□ CALCULATED INTERACTION IMMEDIATE
◇ GALACTOSE ALONE
○ GLUCOSAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE ALONE

FIG. 2

of a complex is also indicated by the appearance of an absorption peak at 262 μ .

In the case of the mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone and D-glucosamine, no significant change could be detected even up to one hour after mixing the two solutions. The absorption curve of the mixture was found to overlap the calculated curve, but when the mixture was incubated at 30° for 3 to 4 hours, a difference between the two curves became more prominent, indicating the slow progress of the reaction (not shown in the figure). After about 24 hours, the observed and calculated curves became distinctly different. The reaction in this case appears to be rather delayed and the new curve shows a flat absorption maximum ranging from 255 to 285 μ (Fig. 2). The occurrence of a peak in this region, however, indicates the possibility of a definite reaction.

Works on the chromatographic isolation of the complex and its characterisation are in progress.

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